

Zootopia - Verbal Adaptation 2

Fifteen years later.

It is Judy's first day in the police academy. Many young animals are there, ready to train. The instructor looks at them and says: "Look around, students! In one month, one of you is going to give up. And this year it is easy to guess who." The class looks at Judy, she is the smallest by far. Some animals whisper: "He, he, he." "Poor little rabbit."

The instructor shouts: "Remember! If you fail in school, you just fail. But if you fail in the real world... you are DEAD!" Judy stands quietly, her ears low.

The first task is to climb a big ice wall. The instructor shouts to Judy: "What are you waiting for, farm girl? Climb that wall!" Judy tries hard but fails. The instructor yells: "You are DEAD, carrotface!"

Judy continues with other exercises. They are all very hard for a tiny animal. Judy cannot finish any of them. Each time she fails, the instructor shouts: "DEAD! DEAD! DEAD!"

In the final training, Judy fights against a rhino. She tries hard, but she falls after one single punch. The instructor yells: "DEEEEEAD!"

Time passes.

Judy trains hard and studies hard. Every day, she is faster, more athletic, stronger, and smarter. She does better in the tasks. Even her instructor says: "Good job, farm girl!"

Judy fights the rhino again. She dodges the punches of the rhino and uses the ropes to jump with extra force. She pushes the fist of the rhino and he punches himself "POW!" The rhino falls. Judy wins!

At the graduation, the mayor, a great lion, comes to speak: "As mayor of Zootopia, it is a big honor to be here today. Because I want to introduce..." He looks at the crowd and points to Judy: "...Judy Hopps, the first rabbit cop." She is wearing her police uniform and smiling. Everyone claps for Judy. The mayor finishes his speech saying: "Small size. Big determination."

To be continued.